

COMPARISON OF UZBEK TRADITIONAL ASSESSING SYSTEM AND CREDIT MODULE SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

This article describes the formation of the credit-module system, its content, forms of process, the expected results of the system, the gradual transition to a credit-module system in Uzbekistan and compare classical module of assessment with the contemporary credit system.

The coronavirus outbreak is causing unprecedented changes in every aspect of human life. Additionally, these sets were responsible for the "break" of long-standing traditions, values, and ideals. In particular, the educational system directly contributes to the advancement of science and knowledge. The effectiveness of the educational system is directly impacted by the quality of the teachers, the demand for students, the content of the instructional materials. During this period, students stayed at home as well as other people in the world. This made some inevitable changes in education system. The pandemic posed authority as well as teachers to think about new ways, methods and techniques to teach students in a distance, consequently, the way of online learning is developed. Moreover, this indicates that the training program produced in the training camps is closely tied to the growth of advanced personnel, improving their competitiveness in line with labor market expectations, and nurturing specialists with innovative

thinking. The procedure for using the credit-module system has been the most effective way in assessing students' knowledge and required their independent approach to the lessons.

The credit-module system, which organizes education through a combination of credit measurement and teaching module technology, is an assessment paradigm. Its total implementation is a multifaceted, complex systemic process. The credit-module idea prioritizes two important issues: ensuring students' independent performance and rating-based evaluation of students' knowledge. A module covering a range of subjects and courses is part of the curriculum. It is a combination of various disciplines (courses) created to equip students with the skills needed to form logical and analytical inferences. The teacher arranges and maintains the students' daily routines in addition to developing the curriculum and delivering courses in real time through video and audio. The student also completes the

assignments and studies the subject independently.

The implementation of the Credit module system gives students more independence as well as the chance to autonomously organize their academic progress in order to become competitive specialists in their chosen fields in the future. Additionally, it resulted in advancements in instructional technology and the evaluation system. The credit system is widely used in the education system of Uzbekistan according to the presidential decree on October, 2019

"As soon as the Concept of higher education system development of the Uzbek Republic till 2030, at least 10 institutions of higher education in the Country will be in the list of 1,000 renowned internationally recognized organizations". It is also expected that by 2030, 85% of all higher education institutions (HEIs) in the country, including 33 higher education institutions in the 2020/2021 academic year, will be transferred to Credit Module system.

Characteristics of traditional and credit module systems in Uzbekistan

CLASSICAL MODULE	CREDIT MODULE
Paper based controlling system	Organizing educational procedures in a modular manner;
Different attitudes towards special and non-special subjects	Evaluating the importance of a single subject
Ongoing work of students, mid-term, and final assessed work	Assessment of students' knowledge on the basis of rating points;
Less involvement of individual learning in educational process	Increase the contribution of autonomous learning in the educational process;
Education process is not verified	Improve quality of education and assurance
Guidelines on marking system and monitoring students' performance. Feedback of students is taken into consideration	Students are permitted to choose their own classes.
The curriculum isn't directed to prepare students for the world of work	Convenience of educational opportunities and flexibility to modify based on the market's need for specialists
Based on national standards demands	Complete disclosure of learning goals and assignments;
Requirement of qualification to be acquired at the end of the subject	Requirements for the qualifications of the student to be acquired at the beginning and end of the subject (course);
No specific guidelines or manuals	The module includes the subjects of lectures, seminar schedules, and practical assignments and exercises for evaluating independent learning;
Course delivery is assessed by regular teaching observations by the head of department, experts, and lecturers	Provide students with academic freedom in choosing science programs. In the credit system, all undergraduate subjects are combined into three cycles:
35% of revising general knowledge in the bachelor's program in all directions;	25% of the cycle of general education subjects in the bachelor's program in all directions;

In the multi-level system of higher and postgraduate education (bachelor, master, PhD), an individual often gains a broad knowledge base in a particular field before enrolling in specialized training programs that are narrowly focused on the specialty. In terms of educational concepts and approaches, such a system enables the student to gain interpersonal skills and competencies during the course of their academic career. It offers an appropriate and straightforward application of knowledge.

Universities also benefit from the ECTS (European Credit Technology system) in a number of ways. It makes particular efforts to ensure that curricula are comparable, different, and appropriately reflect the understanding of the educational process in a particular field of study and competence. It also allows for pre-negotiation of the program content at the higher education institution where they are accepted and sent in order to get the student's degree recognized. In handling every aspect of the educational process, the learner maintains ownership and freedom. In the European educational system, courses and the entire educational process are measured in credits, however in Uzbekistan and other CIS countries, academic hours are used. The ECTS determines the number of credits for each higher education institution's credit scheme.

Therefore, in higher education, professors focus on acquiring data, processing it, and then educating students about it. Specifically, instructors just receive and convey information. In this scenario, the student spends the majority of his time in class listening to lectures as an information receiver and an object of the educational

process. Today's challenge of fostering students' independent learning is brought on by the accelerated access to information, the increase of access to worldwide scientific and technical databases, and the accelerated globalization. Increased commitment and demand for university teachers will result from the transition to a credit-modular educational system. As was previously stated, an instructor employing a modular learning system performs not just administrative and informational tasks but also serves as an advisory and coordinating role. The teacher's central position in pedagogy is maintained.

CONCLUSION

Student interchange program improves the system of educational credits. Students can transfer between colleges without damaging their credit because of one-time financing that has been credited to another institution. The system removes challenging administrative barriers and allows Uzbek students to continue their education at prestigious universities abroad. It's crucial to remember that any direct application of international experience is done on a case-by-case basis and is never done without carefully examining its component elements and without taking into account our own principles. This does not imply that this method is entirely in line with our beliefs, circumstances, and principles that strive to develop a person in harmony. As active participants in the educational process, teachers and students, whose opinions need to be changed.

References:

1. Urinov V. ECTS credit-module system in higher education institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan: Basic concepts and rules. –T.:2020.
2. Jessica Shedd (2003), "The History of the Student Credit Hour". New Directions for Higher Education. 122 (Summer) (122): 5-12.

3. Resolution of The Council and of the Ministers of Education, Meeting within the Council, Official Journal of the European Communities, 1976.
4. Robert Wagener, A History of ECTS, 1989-2019. Developing a World Standard for Credit Transfer and Accumulation in Higher Education. International European Commission ECTS Guide of 2015. Available at https://ec.europa.eu/education/ects/users-guide/docs/ects-users-guide_en.pdf
5. European Commission ECTS Guide of 2009.
<https://ec.europa.eu/education/ects/users-guide/docs/year-2009/ects>
6. <https://www.uc.pt/ae3s/pastadocs/ects-users-auidel70804.pdf>